

INVENTORY MANAGEMENT TECHNIQUES AND ORGANIZATIONAL COMPETITIVENESS OF OIL AND GAS COMPANIES IN SOUTH-SOUTH, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *Inventory Management Techniques enable organizations to identify and mitigate competitive strategies in critical operational systems, reducing the risk of high costs and ensuring cost leadership in the industry. Inventory management techniques is the independent variable and organizational competitiveness the dependent variable is measured with cost leadership and cost reduction. The study adopted a cross sectional survey research design, the population of this study comprised the twenty-four (24) oil and gas companies operating within South-South Nigeria as enlisted in the finelib.com Nigerian Directory and Search Engine (2022). Based on the small size of the population, the study adopted the entire population as the sample size. However, a Census method was adopted in administering three copies of structured questionnaire to Operations Managers, Procurement/Logistics Managers and Marketing Managers from each of the 24 oil and gas companies in South-South, Nigeria. This means that a total of 72 respondents were used for the study. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to determine the relationship between the variables with the aid of (SPSS) version 23.0. The findings from literature and analysis revealed that a positive relationship exists between inventory management techniques and organizational competitiveness. In conclusion, inventory management techniques contribute to competitiveness of oil and gas firms in South-South Nigeria. By maintaining optimal inventory levels, companies can enjoy cost leadership and reduction in cost of production by avoiding both overstocking, which ties up capital and stockouts, which can*

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lead to costly delays. The study therefore recommends that oil and gas firms in South-South Nigeria should emphasize greater attention to the degree of inventory management techniques in enhancing overall performance and as a result increase organizational competitiveness.

INTRODUCTION

The Nigerian oil and gas sector, a critical pillar of the nation's economic foundation, is made manifest by its global significance, operational intricacies and susceptibility to various externalities. The industry has long been a cornerstone of the nation's economic development, contributing significantly to government revenue, playing a crucial role in the global energy market (Orazulike, Orajaka, & Ibe, 2020). Today, Nigeria is regarded as one of the strongest economies in sub-Saharan Africa due to the influence of oil exploration activities and the development of oil industry in Nigeria. It is also important to add that the oil and gas industry has contributed significantly to the socio-economic comfort of Nigerians despite challenges such as fluctuating oil prices, security issues and regulatory uncertainties (Osoro, Muturi & Ngugi, 2016). Wamoto, Kwasira and Ndolo (2023) note that the oil and gas sector fosters a great impact in the economy via inter-sectoral linkages through provision of energy to industries and machines, employment generation, for the teeming Nigerians, foreign exchange earnings through export of crude oil. Effective inventory management is regarded by Ambe (2012) as one cardinal success factor

which cannot be neglected in supply chain management practice. Inventory constitutes the most significant part of current assets within the oil and gas industry. Ohaka et al (2020) defined Inventory management as an aspect of cost control and of cost reduction, when stockholdings costs are excessive. Inventory comprises a large part of a business working capital and therefore, it is very important to manage it effectively. Musara (2012) describes inventory management as a mechanism that provides efficient and effective services at safer and faster rate. Adoption and implementation of inventory management principles can benefit manufacturers in reducing costs and improving customer service as well as sales performance (Banerjee, Kim & Burton, 2007). Prudent management of inventory reduces depreciation, pilferage, and wastages while ensuring availability of the materials as at when required (Ogbadu, 2009). Inventory management is critical to an organization's success in today's competitive and dynamic market. This entails a reduction in the cost of holding stocks by maintaining just enough inventories in the right place and the right time and cost to make the right amount of needed products. High levels of inventory held in stock affect adversely the

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procurement performance out of the capital being held which affects cash flow leading to reduced efficiency, effectiveness and distorted functionality (Koin, Cheruiyot & Mwangangi, 2014).

Organizational competitiveness is the ability of a firm to continuously improve its capabilities and deliver a better value to customers than its competitors (Gupta et al., 2016). It is the degree of superiority which a firm has over its competitors in the marketplace (Onyemenam, 2004). According to Tarus et al, (2017), a firm that is unable to compete favorably in the market has already ensured its candidacy for corporate collapse. Improving organizational competitiveness requires firms to increase their level of market leadership, cost leadership, differentiation, and outperform their competitors. The global interconnectedness of the oil and gas industry exposes it to various vulnerabilities, these challenges necessitate a thorough examination of strategies adopted by oil and gas companies to improve their organizational competitiveness. Recent events, such as oil price fluctuations and supply chain disruptions due to global crises, underscore the vulnerability of the industry (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development OECD, 2021). The inventory management philosophy emphasizes excellence among manufacturing companies through the continuous reduction of waste and reduction of

inventories as well as consistent improvement in productivity (Umar, Gunasekaran & Subramanian, 2021). Unfortunately, implementing the inventory management philosophy is difficult due to the misunderstanding and misinterpretation of the core of the concept by local manufacturers in Rivers State and Nigeria at large (Farahani & Elahipanah, 2008). This study sought to investigate the nexus between inventory management techniques and organizational competitiveness of oil and gas companies in South-South, in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The oil and gas sector is seen as a major apparatus of economic growth and development in Nigeria. The sector is regarded as an economic player with multiplier effects on education, transportation, tourism, construction among other sectors in the country (Duru, 2010). The industry is characterized by regulatory complexities, market volatility and operational challenges and requires the effective management of inventories that holds significant implications for supply chain operations and overall organizational performance.

The failure of most of these companies to fully adapt to inventory management techniques in their organizations have affected the availability, delivery, cost and competitiveness. Prior researches on inventory management techniques and organizational competitiveness of oil and gas

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companies is still modicum. Most studies in this area were conducted in other geographical zones of the country. The South-South geographical zone of Nigeria, consists of six (6) states; Rivers, Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta and Edo.

This study filled this gap by exploring the empirical relationship between inventory management techniques and organizational competitiveness of oil and gas companies in South-South, in Nigeria.

Conceptual Framework

Conceptual framework of the relationship between Inventory Management Techniques and Organizational Competitiveness of Oil and Gas Companies in South-South, Nigeria

Source: Measures of organizational competitiveness adopted from Bertuzzi, 2015

Theoretical Foundation of the Study:
Lean Inventory Management Theory

A theoretical framework refers to the manner in which the researcher develops thoughts on what

the possible answers could be and these thoughts and theories are then clustered into themes that frame the subject. Different theories have been employed to help bring out clarity to the study of the effects of vendor managed inventory on competitiveness of many organizations (Nsikan et al., 2015). In this study, the Lean inventory theory, an extension of Just-in-Time, a philosophy of inventory management that emphasizes the need of maintaining minimal

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inventory in accordance with production requirements by (Eroglu & Hofer, 2011) was used to explain the relationship between vendor managed inventory technique and organizational competitiveness. The lean inventory theory aims to minimize costs in an organization's inventory system by making choices related to production, storage and the whole supply chain (Troxell, 2015). Jolla (2014) stated that the Lean theory is based on the concept of Economic Order Quantity (EOQ), which aims to optimise inventory levels by identifying the most suitable order quantities over a certain period of time. The theory highlights the potential for the operating system used to monitor inventory levels and different inventory items to be dynamic and adaptable to changing requirements. Rashmi et al (2021) contended that using lean theory is crucial for achieving greater performance. The lack of efficient inventory management is a significant issue encountered by business sectors in developing nations like Nigeria. A large proportion of these enterprises do not use even the fundamental ideas and procedures of inventory control (Wangari, 2015). The lean theory is criticized for the need of a tight and longterm cooperation and information exchange between a corporation and its trade partners. When materials are effectively planned and managed, it positively impacts delivery timelines

and efficiency. Therefore, the lean inventory theory was used to provide theoretical elucidation for the theme of this research. This decision was based on the need to analyse the impact of inventory management on operational performance, thereby requiring a cautious approach to inventory control. The theory helps us to understand the structure and dynamics of supply chain networks within the oil and gas industry in improving inventory management techniques and firm's competitiveness.

Concept of Inventory Management Techniques

Abara (2011) defined inventory as a stock of resources used to facilitate production or to satisfy customers' demand. Inventory refers to stock of anything necessary to do business (Pandey, 2011). Pandey further stated that stocks represent a large portion of organizational investment which must be well managed in order to maximize profits. According to Ajao (2023), inventory management is a collection of strategic actions executed by the operations manager of a business organization. Its purpose is to guarantee the availability of an adequate quantity of inventory items to facilitate the company's operations in an efficient manner, while also considering cost and optimal utilization. This procedure involves the surveillance of inventory storage, utilization and movement. Inventory management has to do with art and science of maintaining stock levels

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of a given group of items incurring the least cost consistent with other relevant targets and objectives set by management (Lwiki, Ojera, Mugenda & Wachira, 2013). Naliaka and Namusonge (2015) described inventory management as a fine line between the replenishment lead time, carrying costs, asset management, inventory forecasting, valuation of inventory, future inventory price forecasting, physical inventory, inventory visibility, available space for inventory, quality management, replenishment, returns, defective goods and demand forecasting.

Inventory management techniques as one of the supply chain management practices is an activity that organizes the availability of goods to the customers from sales items to consumables and spare parts (Tungo, 2014). According to Waithaka, Mburu, Koror and Muathe (2012), the horizons of inventory management techniques cut across managing the replenishment in lead time, replenishment of goods, returns of defective goods and demand forecasting, carrying costs of inventory, asset management, physical inventory, available physical space, demand forecasting, inventory valuation, inventory visibility, future inventory price forecasting and quality management. With a balanced of these requirements, it is possible to reach an optimal inventory level, which is an ongoing process as the business needs a shift and react to the wider environment (Ogbo, et al,

2014). Inventory management techniques involve the use of many techniques of managing inventories in an organization, these techniques are EOQ method, Stock levels, ABC analysis, Strategic Supplier Partnership, EDI, JIT, EPOS, Bar coding, Lean inventory system, MRP, ERP, automatic replenishment, vendor-managed inventory and VMI. All these methods can be used by any organization in managing inventories (Tungo, 2014). Anichebe (2013) said that one of the biggest obstacles to effective inventory management is determining an appropriate buffer stock due to sales; and this is particularly true in the oil and gas industry. In order to keep up with the organization's consumption pattern of inventories, management must carefully determine the proper amount of safety inventory to maintain.

Concept of Organizational Competitiveness

Lall (2011) defined competitiveness as the ability of a firm to do better than others in terms of profitability, sales and market share. He argues that firm competitiveness is essential for them enhance and defend their position in the market. Organizational competitiveness is also seen as an organizations ability to outperform rivals with an impact on its present market share (Stojcic et al., 2021). Organizational competitiveness is the ability of a company to dominate the market, increase customer patronage and retention and gain a competitive edge over its competitors in

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the market. A firm is said to have competitive advantage over its rivals if its profits exceed the average for its industry (Gitonga, 2012). Hassan (2000) conceptualized organizational competitiveness as the capacity of an organization to increase and sustain its customer base despite the competition from other similar organizations.

Improving organizational competitiveness is a necessity for a company to remain in business and to keep up with its competitors in the market. A company can improve its organizational competitiveness by satisfying its customers, increase its cost leadership strategies, differentiates its products and brand and gain a competitive edge over its rivals. Every company wants to gain a competitive edge over its major competitors. Improving and sustaining organizational competitiveness is crucial to the growth and survival of a company. Every company irrespective of the sector it belongs wants to improve and sustain its competitiveness. Competitive organizations are expected to show higher growth rate in terms of revenues and sales, better returns on investment, higher market share, higher market access and control of distribution as compared to non-competitive firms (Selcuk, 2016). Such organizations are marked by reduced production cost leading to increased profits and have the ability to sell in the market while meeting market requirements. These factors ensure constant

profits with an increasing market share in the face of competition (Pedraza, 2018). The most common criteria used in measuring organizational competitiveness in literature are cost leadership, product differentiation, market leadership, focus strategy, launching new products and services, entering new market segments, forming strategic alliances, customer satisfaction, customer patronage, sales growth, market share growth, customer loyalty and retention (Porter, 1986; Cross, 2012; Benthaus et al., 2012; Bertuzzi, 2015; Roberge, 2014). In this study, organizational competitiveness is measured using cost leadership and cost reduction. These measures are discussed below:

Cost Leadership

Cost leadership is a term used when a firm projects itself as the cheapest manufacturer or provider of a particular product or commodity in a competition (The Economic Times, 2021). Cost leadership does not mean that the organization produces goods which are of inferior quality at comparatively cheap rates, but that the firm produces goods which are of acceptable quality and specific to a set of customers at a price which is much lower or competitive than other companies producing the same product. Cost leadership is being able to be a leader in production cost in the industry (Pearce & Robinson, 2016). Cost leadership tries to keep costs of production as low as possible and yet making efforts in manufacturing quality

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merchandise which get together the customer expectations, taste and preference as argued by Pearce and Robinson (2016). Marangu et al. (2017) suggest that companies achieve lower cost when they are able to produce their products at a lower cost than their competitors. According to Porter (1980) being a leader in cost is being able to lead in production cost in the industry. Cost leadership as a strategy allows the firm to be a low-cost producer and thus making more profits than rivals due to low costs of production and economies of scale. This becomes an advantage for the firm, especially those that are first-movers or those that have ease of access to raw materials or factors of production.

Cost Reduction

Cost reduction denotes real or genuine saving in production, administration, selling and sharing costs resulting to the elimination of wasteful and inessential elements from the design of the product and from the techniques and practices carried out in connection therewith (Gong, 2008). The necessity for cost reduction arises when the profit margin has to be increased without an increase in the sales turnover (Robert, 2016). The aim of cost reduction in any organization is to see whether there is any possibility in bringing about a saving in cost incurred- material, labour, overheads, etc. According to Groves, Collins, Gini and Ketter (2014), cost reduction is to be understood as the success of real and unchanging reduction in the

unit costs of goods manufactured without impairing their suitability for the use intended. Low production cost has become one of the primary ways that organizations compete in a global economy, hence, cost reduction must continually be in the minds of managers of organization (Groves, Collins, Gini & Ketter, 2014).

Gong (2008) state that cost reduction is a planned approach to reduce expenditure. It is a continuous process of examining critically all elements of cost and each aspect of the business with a view to improve business efficiency, cost reduction is a corrective function. Cost reduction is the process of cutting down costs incurred by an organization for the purpose of making profit. It starts when cost control ends and considers that no cost is at its optimum level. In planning for reduction in costs, Adeniyi (2000) emphasized that organizations need to adopt crash programs. Therefore, cost reduction is accomplished in inventory management through lowering costs associated with holding stocks, transporting, warehousing and delivery.

Empirical Review on Inventory Management Techniques and Organizational Competitiveness

Several empirical studies affirm to the significance of inventory management techniques on Organizational Competitiveness. For instance, Sule and Oshi (2022) examined the impact of inventory management and

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competitive advantage in contemporary manufacturing firms in Nigeria. This was done in relation to how effective and efficient inventory management can be used to achieve a competitive advantage in any sector such manufacturing firm may belong. This study being both exploratory and theoretical, critically reviewed inventory management and competitive advantage. The study concluded that in pursuing cost leadership and differentiation as corporate strategies, inventory management must be effective and efficient. There were recommendations based on the findings, that manufacturing firms should be proactive on issues relating to production, creation of a distinct functional department in charge of inventory management and the consideration of the use of scientific approach to inventory management.

Akinlabi (2021) examined the effect of inventory management practices on operational performance of selected flour mills companies in Nigeria. The study adopted cross-sectional survey research design. The target population comprised 2,237 staff of the selected flour mills companies. A stratified random sampling technique was used to select the sample size of 776. The response rate to the 776 copies of the questionnaire administered was 82.6%. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential (Pearson Product Moment Correlation and Regression Analysis) statistics. Findings revealed

that inventory management practices positively and significantly related to operational performance. The study concluded that inventory management practices significantly influenced operational performance of flour mills companies in Nigeria. Ndu and Ajao, (2023) investigated the impact of inventory control on operational efficiency of Hotels in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Specifically, it examined how inventory control could affect timely service delivery, waste reduction and cost reduction which are the identified measures of operational efficiency. The study adopted the descriptive survey design and used the cluster sampling technique to draw a sample of three hundred and eighty-five (385) from fifty-five (55) hotels within the sector. The hypotheses were analysed using Partial Least Square structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM). The result showed that inventory control possesses a significant positive relationship with operational efficiency as it boasted of beta (β) values of 0.876, 0.821, 0.804 for timely service delivery, waste reduction and cost reduction respectively. Consequently, hotel managers were urged to design and implement suitable inventory control systems that would guarantee optimality in the usage and storage of inventory items since it was shown to have positive impact on operational efficiency.

Ismail and Halima (2022) to examine the relationship between inventory management and financial performance of industrial

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companies that are publicly traded in Nigeria. The primary emphasis of their investigation was the administration of inventory control within the selected enterprises. The study was centred on the examination of how inventory management affected the financial performance of manufacturing companies listed in Nigeria. The research population comprised manufacturing enterprises that were duly registered in Nigeria. An intended sample of 200 employees hailing from the finance and retail departments completed the structured questionnaire. Using the enumeration method, secondary data were acquired. 170 copies of questionnaire, or 85% of the total surveys instrument sent out, were retrieved. The hypotheses were assessed through the application of inferential statistics. Their findings showed that effective inventory management has a substantial positive effect on the financial performance of publicly traded industrial companies in Nigeria. It was recommended that managers strengthen their strategic partnerships with suppliers and deploy resilient automated security protocols to oversee the movement of products across the entire organisation. On their part, Folajimi et al (2020) stated that inventory accounts for a major portion of production costs incurred by companies. This study looked at publicly listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria and how inventory control levels affected their financial

performance. The study used a mixed-methods approach, combining empirical survey research with fieldwork. In order to provide a structured questionnaire, 72 participants were chosen using quota sampling techniques. According to the results, financial performance of publicly listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria is greatly affected by inventory management.

Methodology

This study adopted cross-sectional survey research design, where all the variables of study was investigated as a one-time observation. This study population comprised the twenty-four (24) oil and gas companies operating within South-South Nigeria as enlisted in the finelib.com Nigerian Directory and Search Engine (2022). The sample size of this study was the same as the population, since the population is not large. This study however, adopted a Census Method in administering three copies of structured questionnaire to Operations Managers, Procurement/Logistics Managers and Marketing Managers from each of the 24 oil and gas companies in South-South, Nigeria. This means that a total of 72 respondents were used for the study.

A total of 72 copies (100%) of the questionnaire were produced and distributed to target respondents. Out of the 72 copies distributed, 69 copies (96%) were retrieved. Out of the 69 copies retrieved only 67 copies (93%) were used for the analysis as 2 copies were invalid. The use of

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Pearson moment Correlation Coefficient and partial correlation to test the relationship between the variables in the study. The analysis

was aided with the help of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 23.0.

Correlation Analysis showing the Relationship between Inventory Management Techniques and Organizational Competitiveness

	Inventory Management Techniques	Management	Organizational Competitiveness
Inventory Management Techniques	Pearson Correlation	1	.832**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	67	67
Organizational Competitiveness	Pearson Correlation	.832**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	67	67

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output, 2025.

The SPSS output reveals a correlation coefficient of 0.832** between Inventory Management Techniques and Organizational Competitiveness, indicating a very strong positive relationship between Inventory Management Techniques and Organizational Competitiveness. More so, the probability value (0.000) is less than the critical value (0.05), this shows that there is a very strong significant relationship between Inventory Management Techniques and Organizational

Competitiveness. This further implies that Inventory Management Techniques can be used to achieve Organizational Competitiveness among oil and gas companies in South-South, Nigeria

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Correlation Analysis showing the Relationship between Inventory Management Techniques and Cost Leadership

		Inventory Management Techniques	Cost Leadership
Inventory Management Techniques	Pearson Correlation	1	.421**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	67	67
Cost Leadership	Pearson Correlation	.421**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	67	67

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output, 2025.

The SPSS output reveals a correlation coefficient of 0.421** between Inventory Management Techniques and Cost Leadership, indicating a moderate positive relationship between Inventory Management Techniques and Cost Leadership. More so, the probability value (0.000) is less than the critical value (0.05), this shows that there is a moderate significant relationship between Inventory Management

Techniques and Cost Leadership. This further implies that Inventory Management Techniques can be used to achieve Cost Leadership among oil and gas companies in South-South, Nigeria.

Correlation Analysis showing the Relationship between Inventory Management Techniques and Cost Reduction

		Inventory Management Techniques	Cost Reduction
Inventory Management Techniques	Pearson Correlation	1	.484**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	67	67
Cost Reduction	Pearson Correlation	.484**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	67	67

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output, 2025.

The SPSS output reveals a correlation coefficient of 0.482** between Inventory Management

Techniques and Cost Reduction, indicating a moderate positive relationship between

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Inventory Management Techniques and Cost Reduction. More so, the probability value (0.000) is less than the critical value (0.05), this shows that there is a moderate significant relationship between Inventory Management Techniques and Cost Reduction. This further implies that Inventory Management Techniques can be used to achieve Cost Reduction among upstream multinational oil and gas companies in South-South, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

From results of the correlation analysis, it can be seen that there is a correlation coefficient of 0.832** between Inventory Management Techniques and Organizational Competitiveness, indicating a very strong positive relationship between Inventory Management Techniques and Organizational Competitiveness. Again, a correlation coefficient of 0.421** between Inventory Management Techniques and Cost Leadership, indicating a moderate positive relationship between Inventory Management Techniques and Cost Leadership. Also, a correlation coefficient of 0.482** between Inventory Management Techniques and Cost Reduction, indicating a moderate positive relationship between Inventory Management Techniques and Cost Reduction. More so, the probability value (0.000) is less than the critical value (0.05), this shows that there is a moderate significant relationship

between Inventory Management Techniques and Cost Reduction.

These findings relate with the findings of Sule and Oshi (2022) who examined the impact of inventory management and competitive advantage in contemporary manufacturing firms in Nigeria and concluded that in pursuing cost leadership and differentiation as corporate strategies, inventory management must be effective and efficient. Akinlabi (2021) in his work examined the effect of inventory management practices on operational performance of selected flour mills companies in Nigeria. Findings revealed that inventory management practices positively and significantly related to operational performance. The study concluded that inventory management practices significantly influenced operational performance of flour mills companies in Nigeria. Again, Ndu (2023) investigated the impact of inventory control on operational efficiency of Hotels in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Specifically, it examined how inventory control could affect timely service delivery, waste reduction and cost reduction which are the identified measures of operational efficiency. The result showed that inventory control possesses a significant positive relationship with operational efficiency. Consequently, hotel managers were urged to design and implement suitable inventory control systems that would guarantee optimality in the usage and storage of inventory items since it was

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shown to have positive impact on operational efficiency.

Conclusion

Based on the results of this study and to the extent of its consistency with similar empirical studies, this study concludes that inventory management techniques significantly relates with Organizational Competitiveness of oil and gas companies in South-South, Nigeria. In the oil and gas sector, where operations depend heavily on continuous equipment and materials availability, effective inventory management helps ensure that critical components are always on hand, reducing the risk of operational downtime. By maintaining optimal inventory levels, companies can enjoy cost leadership and reduction in cost of production by avoiding both overstocking, which ties up capital and stockouts, which can lead to costly delays.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion drawn from findings of the study, we make the following recommendations:

- i. Proper record on inventory should be maintained all through the inventory life cycle from procurement initiation to usage and replenishment.
- ii. Management of oil and gas companies in South-South, should adopt measures to implement inventory control strategies to

optimize inventory cost and thus enhance efficiency.

- iii. The management of oil and gas firms should design a suitable inventory management process which will enable them to compete favorably in the marker.
- iv. Management of oil and gas firms should commit resources in organizational competitiveness so as to improve on their structures and strategies thereby enhancing their competitive capabilities.

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